

The First Visit of a British Monarch to Turkey: Edward VIII

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Abstract

This paper discusses British King Edward VIII's visit to Turkey in September 1936 and the effects of this visit on Turkish-British relations. It is aimed to evaluate the visit of Edward VIII, the first British king to visit Turkey and to determine the effects of the visit on Turkish-British relations. In the context of the sources of the research, mainly the American and English press and partially the Turkish press were used. Using the comparative analysis method, the news and articles published in the international and national press were synthesized. Since the king's four-day trip to Turkey is followed momentarily by the domestic and foreign press, it is possible to detect every hour of the king's program from the press. As the king's visit was not official, members of the press were largely free to follow the king during the visit. It was concluded that the King's trip to Turkey contributed to the development of Turkish-British relations, as well as aroused repercussions in the national and international press.

Keywords: Edward VIII, Turkey, Atatürk, Anglo-Turkish Relations, Britain

İngiliz Bir Hükümdar'ın Türkiye'ye İlk Ziyareti: VIII. Edward

Özet

Bu çalışmada İngiltere Kralı Edward VIII'in Eylül 1936'daki Türkiye ziyareti ve bu ziyaretin Türk-İngiliz ilişkilerine etkileri ele alınmaktadır. Türkiye'yi ziyaret eden ilk İngiliz kralı olan Edward VIII'in ziyaretinin değerlendirilmesi ve ziyaretin Türk-İngiliz ilişkilerine etkisinin tespit edilmesi amaçlanmaktadır. Araştırmanın kaynakları bağlamında ağırlıklı olarak Amerikan ve İngiliz basınından, kısmen de Türk basınından yararlanılmıştır. Karşılaştırmalı analiz yöntemi kullanılarak konu ile ilgili uluslararası basın ve ulusal basında çıkan haber ve yazılar sentezlenmiştir. Kralın dört gün süren Türkiye gezisi, yerli ve yabancı basın tarafından anbean takip edildiğinden kralın programının her saatini basından tespit etmek mümkündür. Kralın ziyareti resmi bir nitelik taşımadığından, ziyarette basın mensupları kralı takip etmekte büyük ölçüde serbest bırakılmışlardır. Kralın Türkiye gezisinin Türk-İngiliz ilişkilerinin gelişmesine katkı sunmasının yanı sıra ulusal ve uluslararası basında yankı uyandırdığı sonucuna ulaşılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Edward VIII, Türkiye, Atatürk, Türk-İngiliz İlişkileri, Britanya

Introduction

Turkish-British relations had followed a problematic course since the National Struggle period. Although there was no state of war between the two sides, they were never friends during the period. There was no official British support for the Greek invasion of Western

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Anatolia, and neither the invaders were armed with British weapons. However, there was certainly support from British Prime Minister Lloyd George for the Greek invasion of Turkey. Notwithstanding, the Turkish government dealt with the Greek invasion skilfully without creating any trouble with the British. The Greek occupation of Asia Minor resulted in one of the greatest defeats for the Greeks in the history of Greece. More than half of the Greek forces were destroyed by Turkish forces while the remnants of the Greek army were barely able to escape to the Aegean Islands leaving everything behind. There was no more a Greek problem in Anatolia. The next target of Turkish forces was Eastern Thrace, the last part under Greek occupation. There was an allied occupation on the eastern and western sides of Dardanelles, Marmora and Bosphorus. The Turks demanded the withdrawal of the allies from the eastern side of Dardanelles and the demand was accepted by the French and Italian governments, they immediately withdraw their forces from the eastern side. British forces were alone, face to face with the victorious Turkish forces on the brink of war. Turkey was invited to a conference by the Allies to have an armistice. The military representatives of Britain, France, Turkey and Italy met at Mudanya to deal only with urgent military issues and so they did. The Armistice of Mudanya was signed by which Turkey gained Eastern Thrace and Istanbul without war. Although there was no state of war between Turkey and Britain, both sides were ready to fight. While all the great British warships anchored in the Sea of Marmora with their barrels pointing towards Anatolia, right in front of them, more than a hundred thousand men of the Turkish army, which had won a great victory days ago, entered the neutral zone, were waiting for the order to advance.²

During the Lausanne Conference, many issues needed to be settled between Turkey and Britain. Harsh discussions were going on between the representatives of the two countries mainly related to Mosul, the capitulations and the straits issues. After months of negotiations, still there was no hope for an agreement and the conference was interrupted, and all representatives returned home. The second phase of the Lausanne Conference concluded with the treaty and finally, there was no state of war between Turkey and Britain anymore. Although it is not possible to argue that both countries left Lausanne gratified, as they had to give concessions to each other, a long period of controversy ended with an important agreement in all respects. From then on, each country had its many complicated affairs to deal with. With the departure of the last British occupation force from Istanbul on October 4, 1923, a new era started for Turkish-British relations. During the 1920s, except for the Mosul

² William Hale, *Turkish Foreign Policy, 1774-2000*, (London, Frank Cass, 2000), 56-78.

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question, Anglo-Turkish relations continued on a routine level, limited to official contacts. There are many claims that the 1930s had been a period of softening first and then rapprochement in Anglo-Turkish relations. The aggressive Italian policy was one of the fundamental factors that caused the development of Anglo-Turkish relations.³ King Edward VIII's private visit to Turkey served as a symbol of the improvement in ties between Britain and Turkey. On board the yacht Nahlin, where the King and Mrs Ernest Simpson were taking a Mediterranean cruise, it was planned for the King to make a stop at Istanbul in September 1936.⁴ Edward, who was the first English king to visit Turkey, was greeted with enthusiasm wherever he was in Turkey and attracted an exaggerated interest from the Turkish people.⁵ Mrs Ernest Simpson, the American lady who was divorced from her first husband and in the process of divorcing her second husband, accompanied the King during his vacation, causing the holiday to be followed with greater interest by the American press.⁶ It is necessary to mention a study that specifically dealt with Edward VIII's visit to Turkey which was made by Tarık Saygı. Saygı's study, which is mainly based on local press and sources, gives detailed information about the King's visit and stands out.⁷ This paper has been prepared mostly by using British and American press which is the most important difference between the two studies.

British-Turkish Relations Before the King's Visit

The British mandate established in the island of Cyprus and Iraq after the Treaty of Lausanne caused Turkey and England to be border neighbours over these two regions. The Mosul question, which could not be resolved at Lausanne Conference, was the biggest obstacle to the good relations between Turkey and England. For Britain, Mosul meant an important location on trade routes to India with rich oil deposits, while for Turkey, Mosul meant part of the indivisible unity of the country, that was, a corner of the homeland. The

³ Yücel Güçlü, "Turco-British Rapprochement on the Eve of the Second World War" *Belleten*, 2001, 65/242, 263. Doi: 10.37879/belleten.2001.257

⁴ Andrew Mango, *Atatürk, The Biography of the Founder of Modern Turkey*, (New York, The Overlook Press, 1999), 505.

⁵ W. N. Medlicott, Douglas Dakin, Gillian Bennett, *Documents on British Foreign Policy 1919-1939*, (London, Her Majesty's Stationery Office, 1979), "Lorraine to Eden" No. 168, September 05, 1936, p.223.

⁶ "U. S. Beauty Still High in King Edward's Favor" *Lancaster New Era*, September 03, 1936, 10. And "American Girl Attains Place in Royal Circle" *Alton Evening Telegraph*, September 03, 1936, 1.

⁷ Tarık Saygı, "İngiltere Kralı VII. Edward'ın Türkiye'yi Ziyareti ve Bu Ziyaretin İçteki ve Dıştaki Akisleri" Master's Thesis, İstanbul University, 2003. See also; Tarık Saygı, *Atatürk ve Kral*, (İstanbul, Parola Yayınları, 2016).

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negotiations held in Istanbul between the representatives of Turkey and England on the solution to the Mosul problem remained inconclusive. The decision taken at the Lausanne conference decided that the Mosul question should be handled in the League of Nations. Turkey's request of holding a plebiscite in Mosul was rejected. A commission was formed from the representatives of independent countries by the League of Nations and a study was carried out on the problem. Eventually, the League of Nations decided to include Mosul within the borders of Iraq under British mandate. Turkey's economic and military capacity was not conducive to starting a new war against this unfair decision. Turkey had to accept the decision of the League of Nations and renounced Mosul, which was included in the borders of the Turkish National Pact. Ankara Agreement was signed between Turkey and England on June 5, 1926, in Ankara and the Turkey-Iraq border was determined.⁸

Turkish-British relations entered a new era after the Mosul question. There was no problem between the two countries for a long time, and there was no rapprochement or friendship between the two countries. There was almost no relationship between the two countries except for official dialogues until 1929 when the British naval fleet went to Istanbul and the fleet commander and the British ambassador visited Turkish President Ghazi Mustafa Kemal Pasha in Ankara. The visit of British representatives had ended on good terms. The British representatives were well received in Ankara and were sent off well when they left. While Turkey's attempts towards westernization and modernization continued under the leadership of President Ghazi Mustafa Kemal, Turkey tried to become a member of international associations with western states. Thus, Turkey became a member of the League of Nations in 1932 and took part in an important alliance. In the 1930s, another phase was passed in Turkish-British relations. In particular, the aggressive and expansionist policies of Italy in the Mediterranean significantly threatened the interests of Turkey and England in the region. Turkey wanted to obtain the support of England and France against the Italian threat. Upon the increase of the Italian danger, Turkey brought the issue of disarmament of the straits to the agenda and tried to provide the support of England in particular. Turkey, which had followed a correct foreign policy strategy, had achieved results from its efforts and the Montreux Convention regarding the Regime of the Straits was agreed upon on July 20, 1936,

⁸ In order to learn more about Anglo-Turkish relations from the First World War to the Second, See. Daniel-Joseph MacArthur-Seal (2018): "Turkey and Britain: from enemies to allies, 1914–1939", *Middle Eastern Studies*, Doi: 10.1080/00263206.2018.1462166

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as an international agreement related to the government of the Bosphorus and Dardanelles Straits.⁹

King Edward VIII at Çanakkale

Atatürk, who acted on peaceful principles in foreign policy, made some attempts to get closer to England. A condolence telegram was sent by Atatürk on 13 May 1936 to the English King Edward VIII, whose father had died in January 1936.¹⁰ Atatürk sent another telegram to celebrate the birthday of King Edward VIII and he got an immediate response from the King indicating his contentment with the celebration.¹¹ King Edward VIII wanted to learn about Atatürk's birthday, and in the reply given by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Turkey, it was stated that Atatürk's birthday was 19 May 1881.¹² In August 1936, The British embassy has officially informed the Turkish foreign affairs that British King Edward VIII would visit Turkey. The news that the English king was going to visit Turkey was welcomed by Turkey with joy and some preparations were made to welcome the king.¹³ In the application made by the British authorities to the Turkish Ministry of Foreign Affairs on August 5, 1936, it was demanded that the king and the British sea vessels, should have the right to free movement in Turkish waters, and this request was immediately accepted by Turkey.¹⁴ A delegation headed by General Fahrettin Altay was assigned to welcome the British king in Çanakkale and accompany him during his contacts there.¹⁵ The Nahlin yacht carrying the British King entered Turkish waters on September 3, 1936, in the morning.¹⁶ Nahlin, advancing in the company of two British torpedoes named *HMS Grafton* and *HMS Glowworm*, was met by two Turkish torpedoes named Adatepe and Kocatepe.¹⁷

⁹ For more information about Turkish-British relations during 1930s, See. Dilek Barlas & Seçkin Barış Gülmez (2018): "Turkish-British relations in the 1930s: from ambivalence to partnership" *Middle Eastern Studies*, Doi: 10.1080/00263206.2018.1462163

¹⁰ Bilal Şimşir, *Atatürk ve Yabancı Devlet Adamları II*, (Ankara, TTK Basımevi, 2001), 324.

¹¹ *Aydın Tarihi*, No:32, (Ankara, 1936), 27.

¹² Şimşir, *Atatürk*, 361.

¹³ W. N. Medlicott, Douglas Dakin, Gillian Bennett, *Documents on British Foreign Policy 1919-1939*, (London, Her Majesty's Stationery Office, 1979), "Lorraine to Foreign Office" No. 74, August 10, 1936, p.79.

¹⁴ Hikmet Özdemir, *Atatürk ve İngiltere*, (Ankara, The British Council, 2001), 69.

¹⁵ "6ft 5in Turkish Hero" *The Daily Telegraph*, September 04, 1936, 12.

¹⁶ "King Edward Visits the Dardanelles and Goes Fishing" *The Sault Star*, September 02, 1936, 2.

¹⁷ "Kral Edvardın yatı Çanakkalede" *Son Posta*, 3 Eylül 1936, 1.

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Nahlin was first anchored at Suvla, Seddülbahir and Kilya piers.¹⁸ King Edward VIII went ashore at the mentioned piers and toured the battlefield under the guidance of General Fahrettin Altay. English King Edward VIII was accompanied by General Fahrettin Altay during his visit at Dardanelles and Çanakkale until the King went to Istanbul.¹⁹ After Nahlin and the British destroyers accompanying him entered Turkish waters and were greeted by Turkish destroyers, General Fahrettin Altay went to Nahlin and greeted the British king and presented Atatürk's greetings and respects to the king.²⁰ The king and Altay communicated in German which Altay says was interesting as there was the cooperation of British-French against Germany, but still, the King preferred German instead of French. All the people on all the ships on the king's transit route saluted the king. While passing through the area where the wreckage of the British *HMS Triumph* warship, which was sunk in the Dardanelles during the First World War, Turkish sailors asked permission from the British King, expressing that they wanted to commemorate the glorious memories of the British soldiers by holding a minute of silence and throwing a wreath into the sea.²¹ The King happily accepted the offer and they all together showed their respect to the British soldiers. The king took many photographs during his travel, sometimes observed far away with binoculars, and received explanations about the Dardanelles War from Fahrettin Pasha for a long time.²² Then the king went to Seddülbahir, where he was greeted by an enthusiastic crowd.²³ Considering that the king could have lunch in Seddülbahir, preparations were made there, and for this purpose, lobsters from Bozcaada, partridges and sergeant grapes from Ezine, were brought. In addition, the delicious wine and grapes of Bozcaada were presented to the King. After fishing for a while, the King had gone to his yacht and rested.²⁴

King Edward VIII's visit was closely followed by Turkish newspapers. Many pages full of the King's pictures and news about him could be seen during the visit.²⁵ There were

¹⁸ "King Edward in Pilgrimage to Cemeteries at Gallipoli" *Wilkes-Barre Times Leader*, September 03, 1936, 19.

¹⁹ Fahrettin Altay, *Görüp Geçirdiklerim, 10 Yıl Savaş ve Sonrası 1912-1922*, (İstanbul, İnsel Yayınları, 1970), 491.

²⁰ "King Lays Wreath at Gallipoli" *The Victorian Daily Times*, September 03, 1936, 2.

²¹ "King at Gallipoli, Two Days of Feting in Istanbul" *Western Morning News*, September 04, 1936, 9.

²² "Gallipoli Visit, Story of the Battles Retold by Turks" *Liverpool Echo*, September 04, 1936, 9.

²³ "The King at Gallipoli" *Liverpool Daily Post*, September 04, 1936, 8.

²⁴ "Kral Edvardın yatı Çanakkalede" *Son Posta*, 3 Eylül 1936, 8.

²⁵ For a full-page story of the King's visit given with his pictures See. "Büyük Misafirimiz Hoş Geldiniz" *Akşam*, 4 Eylül 1936, 1. For another full-page story of the visit See. "İstanbul büyük misafirimizi candan tezahüratla karşıladı" *Akşam, Second Edition*, 4 Eylül 1936, 1.

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exaggerated praises about the king in some Turkish newspapers.²⁶ Many writers competed with proving that Turkey and Britain were friends for many centuries.²⁷ In one of these news, the English king was described as the most handsome man in the world. In other news, Britain was defined as a friendly state which was never so until then. And in other news, the expression “Great King” or “Great Visitor” was used for Edward VIII.²⁸ The exaggerations in the Turkish press took place in the British press.²⁹ Two special vehicles, one of which was open and the other covered, were allocated to the service of the king to be used during the king's journey on land. After examining both vehicles for a while, the English king preferred the covered vehicle and got into the car with Fahrettin Altay and moved towards the British cemeteries. When Edward VIII arrived at the British cemetery, he took off his hat, examined the tombs for a long time and took photographs, and allowed members of the press to take their photographs as he left the cemetery. Edward VIII travelled the Çanakkale battlefield for a long time, examined the area with maps, and received explanations from Fahrettin Pasha. King Edward VIII, who then went to Çanakkale, was greeted and cheered by a large crowd of people with intense cheers and displays of affection. The people of Çanakkale were happy for seeing the British King.³⁰ Tasman Malcolm Millington, superintendent head of the committee that protects the British colony and British cemeteries in the union established for the safety of the Straits, met with King Edward, and the king thanked the British colony by stating that the tombs were well preserved.

The First Ever British King in Istanbul

King Edward VIII, after he visited the Çanakkale region, departed for Istanbul in the evening with the Nahlin yacht.³¹ King Edward VIII, the first British monarch who visited

²⁶ For an article containing exaggerations about King Edward VIII, See. “Kral Edvardın bir günü nasıl geçer?” *Son Posta*, 2 Eylül 1936, 7. Another news says that Turkey never saw such a visitor, See. “Türkiye halkı böyle bir misafir karşılamamıştır” *Yeni Asır*, 6 Eylül 1936, 1. Another article of praising the King, See. “İstanbul dün gece muhterem misafirin şerefine büyük bir şehriayin yaptı. Her taraf nurlar içinde yüzüyordu” *Akşam*, 5 Eylül 1936, 1. For another article full of rumors See. “Kral Edvardın ziyaretine ait yazılmamış taraflar” *Son Posta*, 8 Eylül 1936, 7. Another article See. “İngiliz Kralı Edvard bugün İstanbulla şeref verecekler” *Cumhuriyet*, 4 Eylül 1936, 1. Another article of praising the King, See. “Haşmetli İngiliz kralı İstanbulda” *Yeni Asır*, 4 Eylül 1936, 1.

²⁷ Reşad Ekrem Koçu, “Türk-İngiliz Dostluğunun 400 Yıllık Tarihi” *Son Posta, Siyasi Kısım*, 4 Eylül 1936, 1. Osman Cemal Kaygılı, “Halk arasında İngiliz dostluğu” *Son Posta, Siyasi Kısım*, 4 Eylül 1936, 4.

²⁸ “Büyük misafir ülkemizde” *Ulus*, 4 Eylül 1936, 1.

²⁹ “We All Know Him” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 03, 1936, 13.

³⁰ “Visit to Battlefields” *Liverpool Daily Post*, September 04, 1936, 8.

³¹ “Voyager” *St. Louis Globe-Democrat*, September 06, 1936, 5C.

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Turkey ever, entered Istanbul and received a greeting that would go down in history. Thousands of Turkish and British flags were flown throughout the city, and mosques and minarets were illuminated with countless electric light globes.³² Numerous people made plans to spend the night on the Bosphorus shores in anticipation of the King's arrival on the Nahlin in the morning. The culmination of a three-day celebration would be a regatta on Sunday that King Edward and Turkish ruler Kamal Atatürk would both be attending.³³ Edward arrived in Istanbul on September 4, 1936, in the morning.³⁴ Comprehensive preparations were made in Istanbul for Edward VIII. According to the Turkish press, the arrival of the English king in Istanbul created a festive mood in the city.³⁵ For this purpose, thousands of people took to the streets early in the morning to wait for the king's arrival, and Turkish-British flags were hung on buildings as an important sign of celebration.³⁶ Istanbul's Moda, Kadıköy, Haydarpaşa and Üsküdar beaches were fully decorated and a large crowd waited on the beach. A large banner with the inscription "Welcome" was hung in Sarayburnu.³⁷ All the ships in the ports were equipped, and the Tophane dock, where King Edward VIII would land, was decorated with Turkish-British flags. Red carpets were laid from the Tophane dock to the place where the king would get into the car. When Nahlin entered Moda bay, he was greeted by the Turkish navy.³⁸

Atatürk went to Tophane dock to meet the English king and waited for the king with great joy.³⁹ Along with President Atatürk, Prime Minister İsmet İnönü, Foreign Minister Tevfik Rüştü Aras, Minister of Interior Şükrü Kaya, Minister of National Defence General Kazım Özalp and Turkey's Ambassador to London Ali Fethi Okyar waited at Tophane dock to greet British King Edward VIII. King Edward VIII left Nahlin, got on a small motorboat and set off towards the Tophane quay.⁴⁰ The king arrived at the quay, and when he took off to leave the motorboat to go ashore, he was helped by Atatürk, who was waiting there, and Atatürk helped him to land by holding his hand. Atatürk and the King had a warm

³² "City Makes Carnival" *Liverpool Daily Post*, September 05, 1936, 11.

³³ "Not-so-terrible Turks" *The Philadelphia Inquirer*, September 04, 1936, 21.

³⁴ "King Edward in Istanbul" *St. Louis Globe-Democrat*, September 05, 1936, 4C.

³⁵ "Kral Sekizinci Edvard İstanbul'da, Şehir Sevinç İçinde Bayram Yapıyor" *Son Posta*, 4 Eylül 1936, 1.

³⁶ "İstanbul büyük şenlik içindedir" *Yeni Asır*, 5 Eylül 1936, 1.

³⁷ "Turkey's Great Welcome" *Western Mail*, September 05, 1936, 9.

³⁸ "The King in Istanbul" *Liverpool Daily Post*, September 05, 1936, 11.

³⁹ "The King and Atatürk" *Liverpool Echo*, September 04, 1936, 9.

⁴⁰ "Kemal Atatürk Welcomes the King, Istanbul En Fete" *The Newcastle Journal*, September 05, 1936, 9.

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handclasp.⁴¹ Atatürk greeted his guest by saying "Welcome, majesty" in French.⁴² As Atatürk and the king set off to get into the car, they were greeted by the enthusiastic cheers of the large crowd that had gathered in the area. The two leaders, who got into the car, set off to the British Embassy Mansion.⁴³ While Atatürk and King Edward VIII were on their way to the British embassy, they were met with intense cheers from tens of thousands of people who had gathered on the route they passed.⁴⁴ Atatürk left the embassy after meeting with Edward VIII for twenty minutes at the British embassy. Atatürk left the British Embassy and moved to Dolmabahçe Palace.⁴⁵

Edward VIII, who had stayed in the British embassy for a short time, left there and went to Nahlin for lunch.⁴⁶ After that, the English King, who left Nahlin, went to Dolmabahçe Palace and paid a return visit to Atatürk.⁴⁷ King Edward used the Duke of Lancaster as incognito during his travel to Istanbul.⁴⁸ King Edward VIII's visit to Atatürk took about forty minutes.⁴⁹ During his visit, the king invited Atatürk to a cocktail party in Nahlin, which was accepted by Atatürk.⁵⁰ Atatürk went to Nahlin with Prime Minister İsmet İnönü, Foreign Minister Tevfik Rüştü Aras and London Ambassador Ali Fethi Bey to attend the king's cocktail party.⁵¹ After the cocktail party that lasted for more than an hour, Atatürk and his entourage returned to Dolmabahçe Palace.⁵² After having dinner at the British embassy, the English king returned to Nahlin and spent the night there. The English king spent the next two days of his visit touring Istanbul and the straits. The king, who came to Tophane quay on September 5, 1936, with his companions, started to visit historical places in Istanbul. The people were not allowed to gather on the quay so that the king could travel comfortably, only the journalists were allowed to wait. The first place Edward VIII visited was the Blue Mosque. The king was very interested in the inscriptions and tiles on the walls of the mosque

⁴¹ "Edward VIII in Turkey" *Omaha World-Herald*, September 05, 1936, 3.

⁴² "Talk in French" *The Daily Telegraph*, September 05, 1936, 11.

⁴³ "King Edward Pays Visit to Istanbul" *The Bangor Daily News*, September 05, 1936, 1.

⁴⁴ "Turkish Delight" *The Philadelphia Inquirer*, September 05, 1936, 5.

⁴⁵ Özel Şahingiray, *Atatürk'ün Nöbet Defteri (1931-1938)*, (Ankara, TTK Basımevi, 1995), 533.

⁴⁶ "Ataturk Welcomes Edward to Turkey" *The Atlanta Constitution*, September 05, 1936, 12.

⁴⁷ "King is Greeted by President of Turkey" *The Pensacola Journal*, September 05, 1936, 3.

⁴⁸ "What name does King Edward VIII of England use when he travels incognito?" *Leader-Telegram*, September 06, 1936, 8.

⁴⁹ "The King's Host" *The Daily Telegraph*, September 04, 1936, 12.

⁵⁰ "Long Talk at the Summer Palace" *The Daily Telegraph*, September 05, 1936, 11.

⁵¹ "Royal Party at Istanbul" *Liverpool Echo*, September 04, 1936, 9.

⁵² "President Aboard the Nahlin" *Liverpool Daily Post*, September 05, 1936, 11.

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and visited all parts of the mosque. Another thing that the king was curious about was the Azan, and just then, two muezzins went up to the minaret and recited the Azan in pairs. The king's visit to the Blue Mosque took about twenty minutes.

The next stop of the king, who left Blue Mosque, was Hagia Sophia Museum.⁵³ The king was very interested in the doors, columns and mosaics of Hagia Sophia and carefully listened to the explanations given to him.⁵⁴ After carefully visiting all parts of the museum, the English king expressed his satisfaction that Hagia Sophia had been converted into a museum. The king's visit to Hagia Sophia lasted for half an hour.⁵⁵ King Edward VIII, who left Hagia Sophia, went to the Grand Bazaar from there. The king, who got out of the car in front of the bazaar, entered the bazaar through the big door. The king first visited the Bedesten and then moved on to the antique shops. The first thing that caught the attention of the king in antique shops was the precious carpets. Turkish coffee was offered to the king, who had carefully examined Turkish, Persian and Silk carpets for a while. After paying attention to more than fifty pieces in the shops, Edward left the area and went to Nahlin for lunch. In the afternoon, Edward preferred to take a tour of the Bosphorus towards the Black Sea. He took many pictures during his excursion, was interested in many details about his surroundings, and was impressed by the beauty of the straits and the Black Sea. Late in the afternoon, Nahlin turned back and was anchored in front of Dolmabahçe Palace. In the evening, Edward left Nahlin for another tour of the city and he went to Topkapi Palace. British King visited all parts of the palace which continued for an hour. After that, the king went to Basilica Palace but it was late in the evening so he did not stay long there and he went to Nahlin. Edward left Nahlin for another tour of the straits in the evening and he went to Park Hotel for dinner after his excursion. After dinner at the hotel, Edward left for Nahlin.⁵⁶

On the afternoon of September 6, 1936, the King accepted the British colony of around one hundred and fifty men led by British ambassador Percy Loraine. After the ceremony, the king went to Moda Bay, where the sea sports were held, he went to the Ertuğrul yacht, which was there, and met with Atatürk. Edward watched the sea sports with Atatürk for a while and then Ertuğrul left for Florya. Atatürk and Edward went to the sea mansion where they took a rest for some time. A cocktail party was given by Atatürk in the mansion in honour of

⁵³ "Famous Palaces Visited" *Liverpool Daily Post*, September 05, 1936, 11.

⁵⁴ "The King's Journey Home" *The Guardian*, September 07, 1936, 9.

⁵⁵ "March of the Ages in Old Istanbul, Where Kemal Ataturk has Welcomed King Edward" *The Western Daily Press and Bristol Mirror*, September 07, 1936, 10.

⁵⁶ "The King in Ancient City of the Sultans" *The Daily Telegraph*, September 05, 1936, 11.

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Edward. Except for Atatürk and Edward, there were İsmet İnönü, Tevfik Rüştü Aras and Percy Loraine during the cocktail party. Edward left the mansion after the party, he went to Nahlin. Edward has decided to leave Turkey by train. Thereupon, Atatürk's special train was put into the service of the king.⁵⁷ After Edward left Nahlin, he moved to Sirkeci station, and red carpets were laid on the way where the king would pass. Atatürk's special train was specially decorated for the king, and all sides of the train were equipped with electricity.⁵⁸ President Atatürk, Prime Minister İsmet İnönü, Minister of National Defence Kazım Özalp, Minister of Foreign Affairs Tevfik Rüştü Aras, Minister of Interior Şükrü Kaya, Minister of Economy Celal Bayar and General Fahrettin Altay went to Sirkeci train station to bid farewell to British King Edward VIII. Just before boarding the train to leave Turkey, Edward thanked Atatürk for the interest shown to him and he invited Atatürk and İnönü to London. Atatürk stated that he wanted to visit England while he added that he would send İnönü almost immediately to London.⁵⁹ And Atatürk did what he said, he instantly decided to send İsmet İnönü to London.⁶⁰ The train carrying Edward departed from Sirkeci Station at exactly 23.45 in the evening.⁶¹ Edward left Istanbul for Vienna from where he would fly to London.⁶²

After the visit of British King Edward VIII to Istanbul, it was indicated in many comments that Anglo-Turkish relations were developing.⁶³ British Ambassador to Turkey, Percy Loraine, reported to his government that the visit could serve the development of Anglo-Turkish relations and that it was a very fruitful one.⁶⁴ King Edward VIII says in his memoirs that when he arrived in Istanbul, Kemal Atatürk, welcomed him and took him on a tour of the city in an open vehicle. His diplomat assured him that it was an uncommon compliment given that Atatürk only rode in armoured vehicles. As this was not a state visit, Atatürk's entertainment was informal.⁶⁵ The King says he got the chance to research Atatürk who had brought about one of the most sudden social revolutions in contemporary history within his country. Edward claims that Atatürk explained to him how he had ended the rule of

⁵⁷ "Edward Leaves Turkey on Presidential Train" *The Morning News*, September 07, 1936, 5.

⁵⁸ "King Edward Concludes Cruise in Adriatic Sea, Leaves Istanbul for Vienna on Personal Train of President Ataturk" *The Baltimore Sun*, September 07, 1936, 7.

⁵⁹ "Ataturk Invited to London, the King's Farewell" *The Daily Telegraph*, September 08, 1936, 15.

⁶⁰ "Başvekilimiz pek yakında Londra'ya hareket ediyor" *Cumhuriyet*, 8 Eylül 1936, 1.

⁶¹ "King Edward VIII Ending Vacation" *Gazette News-Current*, September 07, 1936, 5.

⁶² "Edward May Fly to London" *The Evening Star*, September 07, 1936, 5. For more details about the final hours of the King in Istanbul see. "Sekizinci Edward Dün Gitti" *Son Posta*, 7 Eylül 1936, 7.

⁶³ "Türk-İngiliz dostluğu gün geçtikçe kuvvetleniyor" *Son Posta*, 8 Eylül 1936, 1.

⁶⁴ Michael Bloch, *The Reign and Abdication of Edward VIII*, (London, Black Swan, 1991), 54.

⁶⁵ Philip Ziegler, *King Edward VIII*, (London, Harper Press, 2012), 350.

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the Muslims, done away with the religious clothing, shut down the infamous harems, and granted a very important right of voting for women in Turkey.⁶⁶

Conclusion

The English King Edward VIII had come to Turkey to pay an unofficial visit. The King left Turkey after visiting the places he wanted to see, especially the Çanakkale region. The visit of the British king caused great excitement in Turkey, and great meanings were attached to the visit. The Turkish people showed extraordinary interest in the King and heroically greeted him. Thousands of people gathered on the king's passage routes showed love to the king and presented him with many gifts. The English king acted very cautiously during his trip, he did not eat the Turkish meals offered to him by the citizens, and he preferred his yacht Nahlin for accommodation. According to the information in the Turkish press, the arrival of the British king in Istanbul was welcomed by the people of Istanbul. This is an interesting situation because Istanbul was occupied by a coalition led by the British during the National Struggle period. Therefore, the fact that the people of Istanbul welcomed the arrival of an English king to the city with such enthusiasm is not something that easily could be explained. The visit of the English king was so exaggerated that even the cup in which the king drank coffee was considered a memorable piece. After the King left Istanbul, some Turkish newspapers published full pages of descriptions and pictures of the valuable meeting between the King and Atatürk. They tried to prove that Turkey and Britain were good friends and that they were important to each other. There were many articles in the competition of proving Anglo-Turkish friendship even for many centuries.

The King's visit to Turkey was not an official state visit and it never had an agenda of official negotiations. The King was amused during his visit to Turkey and left with pleasure. Although there are claims that the King's visit was a turning point in Turkish-British relations, there are not many indications of such an inference. Surely the Turkish side was more than happy due to the visit and would like to benefit from it at its best. On the hand, for the British, the King was on vacation and his visit to Istanbul was part of his holiday. Compared to the Turkish press, the British press paid less attention to the visit and kept it at a low level of attention. While the Turkish press competed in praising the King, contrary to that, the British press paid relatively little attention to the king's visit. The Turkish

⁶⁶ Edward VIII, *A King's Story: The Memoirs of H. R. H. The Duke of Windsor K. G.*, (London: Hazel Watson and Viney Ltd. Aylesbury, 1953), 285.

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government and people showed that they were ready to make a new beginning with Britain during the King's visit. For all that, the visit of King Edward VIII was important in many ways. It was the first-ever visit of a British king to Turkey who saw that the Turkish government and people were ready to develop their relations with Britain.

References

Journals

- “6ft 5in Turkish Hero” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 04, 1936.
- “Ataturk Invited to London, the King's Farewell” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 08, 1936.
- “Ataturk Welcomes Edward to Turkey” *The Atlanta Constitution*, September 05, 1936.
- “Atatürk, Majeste Krala Vekilleri takdim ederken” *Son Posta*, 5 Eylül 1936.
- “Başvekilimiz pek yakında Londra'ya hareket ediyor” *Cumhuriyet*, 8 Eylül 1936.
- “Büyük misafir ülkemizde” *Ulus*, 4 Eylül 1936.
- “Büyük Misafirimiz Hoş Geldiniz” *Akşam*, 4 Eylül 1936.
- “City Makes Carnival” *Liverpool Daily Post*, September 05, 1936.
- “Edward VIII in Turkey” *Omaha World-Herald*, September 05, 1936.
- “Edward Leaves Turkey on Presidential Train” *The Morning News*, September 07, 1936.
- “Edward May Fly to London” *The Evening Star*, September 07, 1936, 5.
- “Famous Palaces Visited” *Liverpool Daily Post*, September 05, 1936.
- “Gallipoli Visit, Story of the Battles Retold by Turks” *Liverpool Echo*, September 04, 1936.
- “Haşmetli İngiliz kralı İstanbulda” *Yeni Asır*, 4 Eylül 1936.
- “İngiliz Kralı Edvard bugün İstanbul'a şeref verecekler” *Cumhuriyet*, 4 Eylül 1936.
- “İstanbul büyük misafirimizi candan tezahüratla karşıladı” *Akşam, Second Edition*, 4 Eylül 1936.

Journal of Anglo-Turkish Relations Volume 4 Number 1 January 2023

“İstanbul büyük şenlik içindedir” *Yeni Asır*, 5 Eylül 1936.

“İstanbul dün gece muhterem misafirin şerefine büyük bir şehriayın yaptı. Her taraf nurlar içinde yüzüyordu” *Akşam*, 5 Eylül 1936.

“Kemal Atatürk Welcomes the King, Istanbul En Fete” *The Newcastle Journal*, September 05, 1936.

“King at Gallipoli, Two Days of Feting in Istanbul” *Western Morning News*, September 04, 1936.

“King Edward Concludes Cruise in Adriatic Sea, Leaves Istanbul for Vienna on Personal Train of President Atatürk” *The Baltimore Sun*, September 07, 1936.

“King Edward VIII Ending Vacation” *Gazette News-Current*, September 07, 1936.

“King Edward in Istanbul” *St. Louis Globe-Democrat*, September 05, 1936.

“King Edward in Pilgrimage to Cemeteries at Gallipoli” *Wilkes-Barre Times Leader*, September 03, 1936.

“King Edward Pays Visit to Istanbul” *The Bangor Daily News*, September 05, 1936.

“King Edward Visits the Dardanelles and Goes Fishing” *The Sault Star*, September 02, 1936.

“King is Greeted by President of Turkey” *The Pensacola Journal*, September 05, 1936.

“King Lays Wreath at Gallipoli” *The Victorian Daily Times*, September 03, 1936.

“Kral Edvardın bir günü nasıl geçer?” *Son Posta*, 2 Eylül 1936.

“Kral Edvardın yatı Çanakkalede” *Son Posta*, 3 Eylül 1936.

“Kral Edvardın ziyaretine ait yazılmamış taraflar” *Son Posta*, 8 Eylül 1936.

“Kral Sekizinci Edvard İstanbulda, Şehir Sevinç İçinde Bayram Yapıyor” *Son Posta*, 4 Eylül 1936.

“Long Talk at the Summer Palace” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 05, 1936.

“March of the Ages in Old Istanbul, Where Kemal Atatürk has Welcomed King Edward” *The Western Daily Press and Bristol Mirror*, September 07, 1936.

Journal of Anglo-Turkish Relations Volume 4 Number 1 January 2023

“Muhterem misafirimizin İstanbul ve Çanakkale’yi ziyaretlerine aid muhtelif resimler”
Akşam, 5 Eylül 1936.

“Not-so-terrible Turks” *The Philadelphia Inquirer*, September 04, 1936.

“President Aboard the Nahlin” *Liverpool Daily Post*, September 05, 1936.

“Royal Party at Istanbul” *Liverpool Echo*, September 04, 1936.

“Sekizinci Edvard Dün Gitti” *Son Posta*, 7 Eylül 1936.

“Talk in French” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 05, 1936.

“The King” *Daily Herald*, September 08, 1936.

“The King and Atatürk” *Liverpool Echo*, September 04, 1936.

“The King at Gallipoli” *Liverpool Daily Post*, September 04, 1936.

“The King at Istanbul and Gallipoli” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 08, 1936.

“The King in Ancient City of the Sultans” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 05, 1936.

“The King in Istanbul” *Liverpool Daily Post*, September 05, 1936.

“The King’s Host” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 04, 1936.

“The King’s Journey Home” *The Guardian*, September 07, 1936.

“The King’s Visit to Turkey-First Pictures” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 08, 1936,
15.

“Turkey’s Great Welcome” *Western Mail*, September 05, 1936.

“Turkish Delight” *The Philadelphia Inquirer*, September 05, 1936.

“Türk-İngiliz dostluğu gün geçtikçe kuvvetleniyor” *Son Posta*, 8 Eylül 1936.

“Türkiye halkı böyle bir misafir karşılamamıştır” *Yeni Asır*, 6 Eylül 1936.

“U. S. Beauty Still High in King Edward’s Favor” *Lancaster New Era*, September 03,
1936, 10. And “American Girl Attains Place in Royal Circle” *Alton Evening Telegraph*,
September 03, 1936.

“Visit Battlefields” *Liverpool Daily Post*, September 04, 1936.

“Voyager” *St. Louis Globe-Democrat*, September 06, 1936.

Journal of Anglo-Turkish Relations Volume 4 Number 1 January 2023

“We All Know Him” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 03, 1936.

“What name does King Edward VIII of England use when he travels incognito?”
Leader-Telegram, September 06, 1936.

Books&Articles

Altay, Fahrettin. *Görüp Geçirdiklerim, 10 Yıl Savaş ve Sonrası 1912-1922*. İstanbul, İnsel Yayınları, 1970.

Ayn Tarihi, No:32. Ankara, 1936.

Barlas, Dilek & Gülmez, Seçkin Barış “Turkish-British relations in the 1930s: from ambivalence to partnership” *Middle Eastern Studies*, (2018): Doi: 10.1080/00263206.2018.1462163

Bloch, Michael. *The Reign and Abdication of Edward VIII*. London, Black Swan, 1991.

Daniel, Joseph, MacArthur, Seal. “Turkey and Britain: from enemies to allies, 1914–1939”, *Middle Eastern Studies*, (2018): Doi: 10.1080/00263206.2018.1462166

Edward VIII. *A King’s Story: The Memoirs of H. R. H. The Duke of Windsor K. G.* London: Hazel Watson and Viney Ltd. Aylesbury, 1953.

Güçlü, Yücel, “Turco-British Rapprochement on the Eve of the Second World War” *Bellekten*, 2001, 65/242, 257-312. Doi: 10.37879/bellekten.2001.257

Hale, William. *Turkish Foreign Policy, 1774-2000*. London: Frank Cass, 2000.

Kaygılı, Osman Cemal. “Halk arasında İngiliz dostluğu” *Son Posta, Siyasi Kısım*, 4 Eylül 1936.

Koçu, Reşad Ekrem. “Türk-İngiliz Dostluğunun 400 Yıllık Tarihi” *Son Posta, Siyasi Kısım*, 4 Eylül 1936.

Mango, Andrew. *Atatürk: The Biography of the Founder of Modern Turkey*. New York, The Overlook Press, 1999.

Medlicott, W. N., Dakin, Douglas, Bennett, Gillian. *Documents on British Foreign Policy 1919-1939*. London, Her Majesty’s Stationery Office, 1979.

Özdemir, Hikmet. *Atatürk ve İngiltere*. Ankara, The British Council, 2001.

Şahingiray, Özel. *Atatürk’ün Nöbet Defteri (1931-1938)*. Ankara, TTK Basımevi, 1995.

Journal of Anglo-Turkish Relations Volume 4 Number 1 January 2023

Saygı, Tarık, “İngiltere Kralı VII. Edward’ın Türkiye’yi Ziyareti ve Bu Ziyaretin İçteki ve Dıştaki Akisleri” Master’s Thesis, İstanbul University, 2003.

Saygı, Tarık, *Atatürk ve Kral*, (İstanbul, Parola Yayınları, 2016).

Şimşir, Bilal. *Atatürk ve Yabancı Devlet Adamları II*. Ankara, TTK Basımevi, 2001.

Ziegler, Philip. *King Edward VIII*. London, Harper Press, 2012.

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Appendices

Appendix-I: In this picture, King Edward VIII was being helped ashore by the Turkish President, Kemal Atatürk on his arrival at Istanbul.⁶⁷

⁶⁷ “The King’s Visit to Turkey-First Pictures” *The Daily Telegraph*, September 08, 1936, 15. For more pictures of the King’s visit See. “Muhterem misafirimizin İstanbul ve Çanakkale’yi ziyaretlerine aid muhtelif resimler” *Akşam*, 5 Eylül 1936, 9.

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Appendix-II: British King Edward VIII with Turkish President Kemal Ataturk during their drive through Istanbul.⁶⁸

⁶⁸ "The King" *Daily Herald*, September 08, 1936, 3.

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Appendix-III: British King Edward VIII the Turkish President Ataturk and his cabinet on Tophane Quay.⁶⁹

⁶⁹ "The King at Istanbul and Gallipoli" *The Daily Telegraph*, September 08, 1936, 18.

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Appendix-IV: Atatürk presenting his deputies to the King.⁷⁰

⁷⁰ “Atatürk, Majeste Krala Vekilleri takdim ederken” *Son Posta*, 5 Eylül 1936, 1.